

Sahel Collaboration and Communication Project (SCC)

RESILIENCE LEARNING BRIEF

DEVELOPMENTAL EVALUATION TO SUPPORT COLLABORATION, LEARNING, AND ADAPTING FOR IMPROVED RESILIENCE PROGRAMMING

Developmental Evaluation Approach in Niger and Burkina Faso

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This brief is intended for development practitioners, particularly USAID implementing partners in Niger and Burkina Faso. It is intended to provide them with a basic understanding of Developmental Evaluation (DE) as it pertains to the Niger and Burkina Faso context and how SCC applies this approach.

WHAT IS DEVELOPMENTAL EVALUATION (DE)?

DE is a specific type of evaluation introduced to the evaluation community by Michael Quinn Patton's 2011 book of the same name. DE was developed through iterative learning about better ways to evaluate interventions characterized by uncertainty or complexity where other evaluation approaches sometimes fall short. While DE shares the core characteristics of all evaluations, it differs from summative and formative evaluations that are typically conducted under development and humanitarian assistance projects.

Summative evaluations are intended to validate the program model and measure the effectiveness, impact and cost efficiency of projects. These end-of-project evaluations are primarily used for accountability and making strategic choices about future programming.

Formative evaluations seek to improve project performance by adjusting activities and designing programmatic approaches to the context. These can be used for project planning and mid-term assessment of what is working and not working. Formative research intends to guide design. For example, in Burkina and Niger, formative research is part of the Refine and Implement (R & I) phase of the food security activity. Although formative evaluation can be confused with DE because both seek better outcomes, formative evaluation tends to recommend incremental improvements in efficiency or effectiveness but generally would not question foundational program logic.

Developmental Evaluations seek to contribute to 'developing' something new. This is a continuous process of discovering and refinement of flexible program models based on near real-time evidence and constant reflection on the activity theory of change and associated assumptions. Because backbone projects such as SCC are relatively recent innovations to resilience programming and because of the complexity of portfolio approaches to programming (for example USAID has over 30 IPs), DE is especially relevant to SCC.

REQUIREMENTS FOR DE

DE is most appropriate for new, innovative or transformative models or novel program logic. DE requires clear articulation of principles, assumptions, and programmatic vision. Co-creation of solutions to a context specific problem, analogous to building an airplane while already in the air, is the reason for DE's distinctive focus on high-frequency data collection and interaction with program staff and stakeholders for ongoing iterative learning by doing.

DE is most appropriate in circumstances such as Niger and Burkina Faso, where the context changes rapidly (*coups*, dynamics of violent extremism, effects of climate change, global pandemics). The idea of DE is that an experienced and methodologically capable evaluator (or team) can help the activity to navigate the environment and still achieve expected impacts, sustainable and scalable change. DE requires senior evaluators who have the experience and skills to understand how to respect principles while flexibly using tools. Principles include being utilization-focused, people-centered and iterative. The evaluator uses a range of tools, some examples included:

- Outcome harvesting/mapping: As an example, we might want to know which activities SCC conducts have produced the greatest value to IPs.
- Positive/Negative deviant analysis: This approach attempts to identify successes/failures and then to analyze the causes of these outcomes. For example, though women might be included in

village development communities, there may only be a small number of committees where women have confidence in their voice and exercise it. These positive deviants would be compared to non-deviants on personal characteristics of women as well as the types/quality of interventions.

- Participatory rapid appraisal: an example is a complementary survey where field teams conducted an interactive conversation with IPs on their perceptions of SCC activities.
- Case study methods: promising practices are frequently studied using case study techniques. In this situation promising practices are identified through informal, sometimes unstructured observations. A more in-depth exploration of whether or not these practices are good or best practices as well as some of the explanatory reasons. For example, collaboration between TEV, WFP and RFSAs has been identified as a promising practice. An initial webinar was held to get additional input from the IP community about this model. More in-depth analysis of outcomes such as food security in areas where this collaboration is occurring and comparison areas may be undertaken to complete this case study analysis.
- Document bootstrapping and automated analysis: DE evaluators often analyze project documents, meeting notes and other evidence of partner collaborations. You may have seen SCC collaboration briefs, for example, which analyze various aspects of collaboration among IPs through analysis of metadata.

IN WHAT CONTEXT IS DE USEFUL?

DE is not applicable in all contexts, but is especially important as an approach for a backbone project like SCC. It was developed to be useful in five broad contexts, all a feature of the Sahelian context:

1. Development of an initiative, program, strategy, policy, etc., emerging from an ongoing effort in a particularly dynamic and complex environment;
2. Adapting the foundation of an existing initiative, program, strategy, policy, etc. that was developed in another context;
3. Exploration of real-time solutions to respond quickly to an unexpected major change or crisis (disaster, financial crisis, organizational failure, etc.);
4. Development of an innovation (pilot) that can potentially be disseminated on a larger scale;
5. Major systemic change effort involving multiple scales (e.g. citizens, organizations, local and national governments).

WHY DE IS IMPORTANT

DE is important because it is the only major evaluation approach that fully supports 'learning by doing'. Complexity science and system thinking literature over the past several decades have emphasized the role of uncertainty when intervening in real world contexts and even more when interventions are novel or implementation sites have complicated circumstances or many actors. The most widely accepted approach to achieving results when working with complex systems is to do smaller and more frequent actions followed by an assessment of their expected and unexpected results. This differs from traditional project planning with strict implementation schedules and often rigid multi-year plans. In situations where there is no proven practice, great uncertainty, a history of project failure, or novel policy and program intervention, predetermined program logic and causal chains leading to desired outcomes rarely hold up in real world conditions over any length of time. DE is important because it can rapidly adapt project activities and promote incremental changes that respond to the complexities encountered while implementing a project. By aligning action to principles and reflecting frequently, there is a greater possibility of achieving the desired outcomes – particularly in complex operating environments.

KEY STAKEHOLDERS

The **Developmental Evaluator** is embedded within the team(s), particularly within the backbone function if it exists. The DE unit helps to steer adaptation and collaborations with evidence.

The **DE Stakeholders** benefit directly or indirectly from the evaluative activities. This includes the IPs, both international and local, and government as well as donors. They all must benefit for DE to be a successful analytical tool.

PROCESS FOR DOING DE BY SCC

SCC THEORY OF CHANGE

IF

- **IF** USAID, USAID implementing partners and country stakeholders agree on shared goals, have a common vision and understanding of resilience as a pathway to achieving those shared goals, and collaborate to reach them; and
- **IF** learning is generated, validated, shared and adopted to improve development activities and policies; and
- **IF** USAID programs and results are effectively communicated to local, regional and national audiences;

THEN

- **THEN** resilience and countering violent extremism interventions, outcomes and impacts will be greater and more likely to be sustained and scaled beyond the support of USAID.

The SCC DE process begins with the interrogation of the Theory of Change (ToC) for enhancing communication and collaboration. Each of the three If statements above need to be validated by various means to determine if the causal hypotheses are valid. That is, do IPs have shared goals and vision that allow them to collaborate, does learning and adaptive management occur and if widespread communication of programs and results actually leads to reduction in violent extremism and increased resilience. These hypotheses are sequential, so the first step is measuring collaboration and facilitators/barriers to collaboration and exploring what roles different stakeholders must take to address barriers and facilitators of collaboration and for SCC, particularly, how SCC can be more effective at fostering collaboration.

Similarly exploring the second hypothesis around learning and adaptation needs to be explored. A first step would best be a document review of IP project documents to identify if and how learning has occurred and the extent to which it has led to improved collaboration and adaptive management.

All of these hypotheses have numerous assumptions, which also will need to be assessed. For example, if project cycles allow opportunities for co-creation and collaboration. A frequent critique

of collaborative work is that each project has its own rhythm that is contractually set, which is a constraint to collaboration. One of the DE activities is to explore the extent to which this impedes collaboration and how to mitigate this challenge.

For these reasons, SCC conducts a number of activities to gauge IP collaboration, learning and adaptation. These may be in the form of requests for documents (for document analysis), various online and in person surveys and learning events, Pause-and-Reflect sessions and After Action Reviews. These activities all are intended to support IPs and other stakeholders to improve collaboration, learning and adaptive management.

CHALLENGES

The authors and practitioners of DE have identified several challenges that the evaluator may face. We present a few of them without being exhaustive:

- **Objectivity:** There is always a trade-off between objectivity and intimate knowledge of an activity. The developmental evaluator is an integral part of an initiative, which is a definite advantage that can turn into a real opportunity to enrich and deepen our understanding of the initiative. However, this kind of proximity can compromise our ability to be objective. For this reason, methods and protocols should be clearly documented and the DE evaluator team should include triangulation as part of the analysis strategy. Triangulation of data sources means that several different sources are pointing to the same conclusions. When possible, the agreement of multiple evaluators is desirable. For example, SCC regularly reviews and triangulates different data sources in developing analyses and learning briefs.
- **Staying results-oriented:** The emphasis on process and the highly variable approach and methodology in DE can lead to a shift away from a results-oriented approach, which is a critical component of the work. DE does look at processes and outcomes. It requires some discipline to maintain an appropriate balance on outcomes. For example, evaluators may focus too much on the determinants of effectiveness of intervention components, such as are they reaching beneficiaries (why or why not) as opposed to identifying those interventions that are having a particularly important impact on food security, nutrition, etc. For example, pause and reflect sessions led by SCC help partners identify emerging results and lessons.
- **Time for external evaluators:** Organizations often expect developmental evaluation results in a time frame more akin to traditional forms of evaluation. However, it takes a considerable amount of time to properly outline and understand the functional relationships between critical variables in a system. The evaluator cannot simply jump in, collect data, write a report and disappear. They immerse themselves in an initiative, participate in meetings, follow up on correspondence, test and develop new iterations of the model, and work with stakeholders to understand and influence complex systems. This is one of the reasons embedded evaluators are preferred. For this reason, SCC's embedded evaluator directly engages in collaborative learning with partners.
- **Negative feedback:** One of the key outcomes of DE is to help focus interventions and identify the most important ones that are likely to be sustainable and scalable. This means that the evaluator will be in a position to deliver bad news to teams managing certain components of the project. For example, if literacy interventions and Savings Groups are gaining the most traction, it may mean that these are the interventions which should receive the most resources during the transition phase of the activity. For SCC, pulse surveys to elicit feedback on meetings and events and data collection on the activities partners find most useful help SCC understand which activities and approaches to continue, adapt or eliminate.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PARTNERS TO ADVANCE DE

- Grant the Developmental Evaluator physical access to teams. In order to be successful, DE teams must be able to meet frequently with IPs in order to continue the research and learning process. For example, SCC DE teams have frequent meetings with IPs to ensure that the Learning Agenda is updated according to evolving learning priorities of IPs.
- Regular meetings with the DE team to stay updated on DE progress, data collection, emerging outcomes, and potential adaptations. SCC's CLA and RL teams maintain regular coordination meetings to adapt the learning strategy.
- Create open communication and information flows. Try not to be a gatekeeper. The success of SCC efforts depends on all partners being open and transparent. In this context of learning and adaptation, it is essential that all partners and their staff members are able to accept failures as a normal part of learning.
- Attention to sensitive data and information from high frequency and unstructured engagements. SCC's DE team is committed to data responsibility and to protecting confidentiality of information provided by project participants and IPs.
- Revisit the DE scope of work periodically. Learning question priorities evolve as does the context of project implementation and collaboration itself. During the implementation of SCC, COVID-19 presented as a large shock to the world and local communities have endured numerous environmental threats and conflicts. New questions, such as those around sustainability and scalability have emerged. IPs and SCC need to ensure that the learning agenda of SCC is most relevant to participants, government, IPs, civil society organizations, USAID and the larger stakeholder community. SCC has included learning questions on DE as part of the project's mid-term evaluation to assess progress and inform needed adaptations.

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